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Research Paper

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Gel Based Face Serum for Dry Skin

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the need for skin care items and therapies has grown significantly. Greater extent. A lot of emphasis has been placed on maintaining a proper appearance and a standard of beauty. Consequently, individual and businesses alike are increasingly inclined to take care of their skin. A cleanser, serum, moisturizer, and sunscreen are the standard components of a skin care regimen. It has been observed that among these, serum are the new standard for creating a great skin regimen. Serum are made for a variety of skin types, including dry, oily, and everything in between This literature's objective review is to emphasize the many advantage of utilizing the appropriate serum composition for people can anticipate . Face serum can quickly penetrate the layer of skin. Herbal face serum is becoming more and more popular among consumers looking for skincare products that are both efficient and environmentally friendly. Serum have a rich, non-greasy composition, a high concentration of active ingredients, quick absorption, and the capacity to penetrate the skin's deeper layers.

INTRODUCTION

Face serum

product that contains a high concentration of active ingredient. It is designed to target specific skin concern such as acne, pigmentation, wrinkles, A face serum is a lightweight, fast-absorbing skincare dryness, and dullness. Because serum have smaller molecules and a thin consistency,

they penetrate deeper into the skin compared to regular creams or moisturizing to enhance their effectiveness. Face serum help improve skin texture, hydration, brightness, overall skin health, making them an essential part of modern skincare routines. Anti-aging Serum is a rapidly advanced field in medical science and applied medicine. Its primary focus is on addressing the root causes of ageing and improving age-related ailments. The

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ultimate objective is to prolong the healthy lifespan of individuals by maintaining youthful characteristics. The study of human skin plays a crucial role in various disciplines such as dermatology, toxicology, pharmacology, and cosmetology. It aims to evaluate the effects of external agents on the skin, including their interaction, absorption mechanism, and potential toxicity on different skin structures. The desire for beauty and good health has been ingrained in society since ancient times. Initially, cosmetics were associated with activities like hunting, fighting, religion, and superstition. Over time, they became linked to medicine. However, relying solely on allopathic medicine has proven inadequate, leading to the need for herbal remedies. Consumers are increasingly aware of the benefits of herbal drugs, herbal cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and natural dyes. Face serum is a lightweight, fast-absorbing cosmetic formulation designed to deliver a high concentration of active ingredients directly to the skin.

Types of Face Serum

The oil serum:

The Oil serum of all the facial serums, the oil serum is the easiest to prepare. Usually, it begins with a base consisting solely of high-quality, quickly absorbing carrier oils, sometimes known as “Dry” oils. The high-quality oils included in the serum have moisturizing and barrier-repairing properties, but they also contain polyphenols, essential fatty acids, and other compounds that the skin may be able to break down.

The serum gel

Gel serum gives the skin a “tightening” feeling, making your customer feel as though certain areas of their face are momentarily tightened or lifted. Because this formulation is water-based, the gel

serum gives you the opportunity to incorporate some amazing water-based (hydrophilic) plant extracts.

The water-based product:

The water-based serums are similar to gel serums, however they could include very little or no gums and thickeners. A water-based face serum would be used to deliver high-performance hydrophilic plant extracts that are embedded against the skin underneath a cream or lotion. Putting an anti-aging face mist under an emulsion and then an oil is the best way to encourage water-based compounds.

The serum emulsion:

The face serum with an emulsion foundation is a moisturizer that delivers high-performance ingredients to the skin while simultaneously enhancing the skin barrier function. An emulsion is made up of two “immiscible” phases—phases like water and oil that don’t want to mix. Water and oil are bound together and kept in a stable form by the application of an emulsifier.

Herbs used in face serum:

Liquorice Root Extract for skin

Because of its antioxidant qualities, liquorice root more especially from substances like flavonoids, triterpene saponins, and glycyrrhizin. These ingredients support a number of skin-improving benefits, including depigmentation, lightening, whitening, anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, moisturizing, acne-fighting, and photoprotective action. Because of its many different skin-improving qualities, using liquorice root extract in your skincare routine has proven beneficial.

Liquorice root extract can help improve your skincare routine. Routine because the extract brightens your complexion, combats aging symptoms, reduces inflammation, and shields your

skin from UV rays. It functions as a hydrating agent and offers UVB protection.

Fig: Liquirice

Taxonomical classification :-

Subkingdom: Tracheobionta

Division: Magnoliophyta

Class: Magnolipside

Order: Fabales

Family: Fabaceae

Genus: Glycyrrhiza

Species: Glycyrrhiza glabra

1. Aloe vera Gel for radiation Protection and Skin care Benefits

Anti-inflammatory effects: It reduces redness, swelling, and irritation caused by UV or gamma radiation. **Protective Effects Against Light rays:** Research possesses shown that it can lessen the harm that radiation exposure causes to the skin.

Anti-aging and moisturizing qualities: Muco polysaccharides, which are present in aloe vera gel, Help the skin hold moisture and stay hydrate. Aloe vera helps protect the skin from UV and gamma-radiation damage. Also increases fibroblasts, which helps stimulates collagen and elastin production, fibers, increasing epidermis suppleness as well as decreasing wrinkles.

Fig: Aloe Vera gel

Taxonomical Classification:

Kingdom: Plantae

Subkingdom: Tracheobionta

Division : Magnoliophyta

Class: Liliopside

Order: Asparagales

Family: Asphodelaceae

Genus : Aloe

Species: Aloe vera

2. Rose Water brighten out skin tone its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory

While rose water can help brighten and even out skin tone due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, it's not a direct skin whitening agent, and it's important to have realistic expectation. Rose water acts as a natural toner that helps maintain skin pH, provides mild astringent action, and enhances skin freshness and hydration.

Fig; Rose Water

Taxonomical classification:

Kingdom: Plantae

Subkingdom: Tracheobionta

Division: Magnoliopsida

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Rosales

Family: Rosaceae

Genus: Rosa

Species: Rosa damascena

3. Glycerin cosmetic preparation provide deep hydration and skin protection

Herbal gel-based face serum is a lightweight cosmetic preparation formulated using natural ingredients that provide deep hydration, nourishment, and skin protection. Unlike creams, serum have a low molecular weight, allowing active ingredients to penetrate deeper into the skin. Glycerin acts as the primary humectant. It attracts moisture from the environment and helps maintain skin hydration for a longer period.

Fig: Glycerin

Taxonomical Classification

Biological Source: Glycerol

Family: Glycerol

4. Vitamin e oil fast-absorbing especially suitable for dry and sensitive skin

Vitamin E oil is an important ingredient in herbal gel-based face serum formulated for dry skin. It acts as a powerful antioxidant that protects the skin from damage caused by free radicals and environmental stress. Vitamin E oil help to nourish and moisturizer the skin by strengthening the skin barrier and reducing water loss, thereby keeping the skin soft and hydrated for a longer time. It also improves skin elasticity, promotes healing of dry and rough patches, and provides a smooth and glowing appearance.

Fig: Vitamin E oil

Taxonomical Classification

Kingdom: Plantae
Subkingdom: Tracheobionta
Division: Magnoliophyta
Class: Liliopsida
Order: Poales
Family: Poaceae
Genus: Triticum
Species: Triticum aestivum

5. Levender Esesntial Oil soothing, moisturizing , and therapeutic property

Levender essential oil for dry skin serum in soothing, moisturizing, and therapeutic properties. Extracted from the flower esesntial oil is rich in bioactive compounds such as linalool and linalyl acetate, which provide anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and calming effects. It also helps to relieve redness, improve skin texture, and provide a pleasant natural fragrance.

Fig: Levender essential oil

Taxonomical Classification

Kingdom: plantae
Subkingdom: Tracheobionta
Division: Magnoliophyta
Class: Magnoliopsida
Order: Lamiales
Family: Lamiaceae
Genus: Lavandula
Species: Lavandula angustifolia

Composition of face serum

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity (100ml)
1.	Aloe Vera gel	50ml
2.	Rose Water	20ml
3.	Glycerin	10ml
4.	Vitamin E oil	5ml
5.	Levender oil	5-8drops 0.5ml
6.	Licorice Exatract	10ml

Method of preparation

The selection of material in the preparation of Herbal gel based face serum for dry skin used in herbal constituent.

Step1: preparation of Liquorice Extract.

1. Take dried liquorice root powder.

Fig: Licorice root powder

2. Add 100ml distilled water or hydroalcoholic solvent.
3. Heat on water bath for 30 minutes.
4. Filter using muslin cloth or whatman filter paper.

5. Concentrate filtrate to obtain required 10ml extract.

Step 2: Preparation of serum.

1. Take a clean, dry beaker.
2. Add Aloe vera gel.

Fig: Aloe vera gel

3. Add Rose water slowly with continuous stirring.

Fig: Add Rose water

4. Add Glycerin and mix uniformly.

Fig: Add Glycerine

5. Add prepared Licorice extract and stir properly.

Fig: Licorice extract

6. Add Vitamin E oil slowly with stirring.

Fig: Vitamin E Oil

7. Finally add Lavender essential oil.

Fig: Lavender essential oil

8. Mix thoroughly until uniform gel consistency is obtained.

Fig: Gel based Face serum

9. Transfer into sterilized airtight container.

Evaluation Test:

Appearance Check

The serum was visually examined for colour, clarity, homogeneity and presence of any particles.

pH Determination

Proper pH keeps the serum for skin, prevents irritation, helps active ingredients work well, and ensure good absorption and stability. The pH of the herbal face serum was found to be 5.3 which falls within the ideal range of 5.0 to 6.0 for human skin. This confirms that the serum is mild, non-irritating, and suitable for dry skin.

Fig: pH test

Viscosity

Check if the serum too thick or too runny. Viscosity play an important role in the sprayability and application consistency of the product.

Organoleptic Properties

The Organoleptic properties of the serum were observed to evaluate its physical acceptability. This included assessment of colour, odour, and appearance. The serum should have a pleasant natural fragrance derived from its herbal ingredients, a consistent colour without any discoloration, and a clear or uniformly dispersed appearance without any sediments of phase separation.

Irritancy

Indicates formulation is safe for topical use on dry and sensitive skin. No redness, itching, or burning observed.

Phase Separation

The prepared preparation was kept in a closed container at room temperature from 25 to 1000°C protected From light. Phase separation was them checked after 24 hours. Changes in phase separation were observed.

Washability

A small amount of the prepared herbal gel base face serum is applied evenly on the skin surface. After allowing it to remain for about 1-2 minutes, the applied area washed gently with water. The skin is then observed to check whether the serum is easily removed without leaving excessive residue or oiliness.

CONCLUSION

The successfully formulated and evaluated a herbal gel-based face serum for dry skin using natural ingredient such as aloe vera gel act as a natural moisturizing base, rose water and glycerine enhanced skin hydration. Licorice extract provide skin-brightening and smooth properties, and vitamin E oil contributed antioxidant and skin-repair benefits. Levender essential oil also added mild fragrance and antimicrobial activity. The evaluation parameter such as pH, appearance, spreadability and stable, safe, and skin-friendly, particularly suitable for dry skin. The pH was found to be within the acceptable range for topical skin preparation. Overall, the face serum demonstrated good moisturizing potential, natural skincare product for managing dry skin. Further clinical studies may help to confirm its long-term efficacy and safety.

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